

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF IMPROVING ELEMENTARY SCHOOL MUSIC LITERACY IN THE PROGRAM "MUSIC CULTURE"

Abdullayeva Aygul Makhan qizi

Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami

Master of "*Music education and art*" direction

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Annotation: in this article, the theoretical basis for improving elementary-grade music literacy in the program of the discipline "music culture" is indicated as an important factor, providing feedback on how important the activities of the music industry are.

Keywords: music basket, form, genre, pause, tempo, repriza, dynamic tone, diction, tone, composer, performer, listener.

Introduction:

Achieving the educational influence of music.

The role of music education in the formation of a child's personality is also incomparable. Since Shun-day, increasing efficiency in the teaching of this subject, focusing on the student's focus on education, places special responsibility on teachers of music culture. The organization of the activities of the music savodi in music lessons at the required level ensures that in the processes of practical activities of the lesson, knowledge and concepts related to this activity are effective in every way to be communicated to students. As you know, each activity in a music lesson has its own goals and tasks that it sets for itself. By listening to music, students form the most necessary knowledge and concepts, such as the structure of music, its shape, genre, the character of the idea of the work. In turn, these knowledge and concepts go from Essence to theoretical knowledge. The means of expression of music, the writing of a note stretch, pauses, lads, tempos, measures, reprisals, dynamic tones are meant by diction, sound, ensemble, etc., and their rules are mastered. It can be seen from this that these types of activities interact to show their influence in strengthening students' knowledge and skills in music literacy. To a certain extent, these activities can be said in the practical view and continuation of the activities of the music industry dab. Achieving the educational influence of music, instilling interest in music in students, strengthening the desire to master expressive means that illuminate musical artistic images in the process of perceiving music are some of the most important tasks facing musical education. Theoretical knowledge of music literacy is also an important factor in expanding the spiritual world of students.

To increase students' interest in music, their mastery efficiency, teachers should plan classes with the following aspects in mind:

- formation of a general understanding of the musical basket in students in theoretical training and knowledge of notes;
- teaching musical instruments in groups according to their nature;
- the use of musical works familiar to students in the formation of conducting rules and skills.

In addition, teachers should pay special attention to the fact that in practical classes, students perform the types of activities of listening, singing in a team, rhythmic immersion in music.

Before teaching singing, sound tuning exercises are performed. In this case, it is sung in a musical form, putting words instead of notes to achieve a pure, clear tuning of the voice and not exhausting the reader. Such singing also ensures the development of the pronunciation of students. Sound tuning exercises can be made up of poetic verses, quick sayings, game numbers close to children. But it's also a little wrong that children only say words instead of notes in my eyes. Because the child needs to know the name of the note, its location, how it is sung. For this, it is advisable for the child to have a musical literacy. It should also be given an understanding of the rules for proper breathing and exhaling. To get the breathing technique right, children are advised to do a balloon blowing exercise.

In elementary grades, the range of musical works should be in the Quinta range, not exceeding the Sexta interval. After vocal tuning exercises, one can switch to singing instruction. In this case, a brief information about the text and authors of the song is first given in a conversational manner. The conversation gives readers a complete understanding of the topic, helping them develop the skill of expressing feedback. It is recommended that the rhythm of rhythmically challenging songs be first studied with the help of a bat and then repeated with words, and that the melody path be taught once the word and rhythm are clearly mastered. And in the practice of the musical savodi, I think that the student's interest in music will increase even more if knowledge about notes is enriched later, gradually introducing them to National Instruments.

In elementary grades, it is possible to carry out such types of activities as listening to music, creativity of music and the departure of children to musical instruments after practical classes, taking into account the rapid exhaustion of the child of course, but for this the school must have a sufficient base. While

musical instruments have been supplied to schools but the scarcity of a class hour is somewhat of a challenge.

Improving musical aesthetic education in the process of general music education depends on the content of the works that students listen to and the attitude towards this music. Nevertheless, on the basis of the above circumstances, the need for a process of sufficiently forming students' interests in folk music is growing. In the process of teaching various classes at different educational stages, there are scientific and methodological works aimed at the issues of aesthetic education of students through various means. However, in the process of elementary grades music lessons, there is relatively little literature on the issue of how students can sing simple songs through the means of notes to form literacy. Familiarization with the musical basket is the main educational criterion, considering the readers the history of the creation of the work being performed, the author, the form of the work, its logical content, the harmony of images in it, the emotional perception of the work, its attitude to it, the perception of the content of the work, its aesthetic impact on oral or written – anti-Nazar experts, on the other hand, describe music literacy as such a part of musical education, in which it provides all information about music (its style, forms, elements of expressiveness, writing styles, authors and participants of music, among others). The content of music literacy is understood differently, the ways in which it is taught in practice are carried out with different content. In some cases, elements of musical literacy are introduced from the first lessons (e.g., musical sounds, its own pitch and stretch, divergence, etc. According to another point of view all theoretical concepts, the idea is put forward that it is advisable that the information is given to children after they have become more closely engaged in it, which is much closer to the music. The educational perdmete of music culture became the one that serves to form the spiritual, artistic and moral culture of students, to carry out national pride and patriotic education, to cultivate creative skill, sophistication, artistic taste, to expand the circle of thought, to educate Independence, Initiative. In later years, the provision of elementary classes to its Classroom Teachers due to a lack of professionals was also a factor in the students' musical literacy dropping for a while. The process of primary education is of particular importance to the formation of musical literacy for students. Because, in the primary class, the main foundation of the student's musical literacy is formed. Organizing the effectiveness of music education requires students to determine their musical abilities. In training, students can learn to listen to music, learn literacy, learn

songs, play children's instruments, perform rhythmic movements, identify abilities that manifest themselves in music-making activities. The teacher should achieve the further development of musical abilities by increasing the activity of students in musical activities, mass involvement of them in training.

Strengthening the desire to master expressive means that illuminate musical artistic images in the process of perceiving music.

It is important for the teacher to approach the lesson in a creative way and set a number of tasks for himself:

- *search for new methods and tools in musical education;*
- *to express the inextricable link between life and art;*

In the implementation of these goals, it is necessary for the teacher to seriously prepare, to work on himself tirelessly, that is, to increase the level of knowledge, to improve the ways of increasing his consciousness by going to scientific literature, new programs, non-fiction, theater, museums (tirelessly). An important role is played by the fact that the classroom in which music lessons are conducted is equipped with taste in an exemplary manner. Technical means, methodological visual aids, piano instrument and Uzbek folk instruments should be summarized, using a new program, drawing up lesson plan synopsis and using new technology. Thus, it is required that the purpose and content of all activities of music lessons are inextricably linked with each other, connecting all parts of the lesson with life, highlighting the content of the lesson. The music lesson is distinguished from other lessons by its artistry, fun and children's more creative pleasure, emotional feelings and the evocation of figurative kechinmalap. Therefore, a music lesson is, first of all, a training lesson. Music classes differ from other classes in the following specific features:

First: it consists of various activities related to music theory and performance: vocal - choral training, music basket, listening to music, playing children's instruments, performing rhythmic movements.

Second: music differs from other types of art in its means of expression, namely "language" (melody, lad, dynamic signs, tempo, alternation signs, intervals). If fiction is expressed in words, visual art in colors, while the art of pacing is expressed in action, music is expressed in the means of melody that arises in musical sounds. When we perceive the above types of art by sight and hearing, we express music only by listening carefully, so that even more mature musicians have matured from the blind.

Third: music is an art connected by a precise measure of time. Therefore, if we are not tuned to the tempo of the music that is played and listen carefully to each

element of it, we cannot perceive the work perfectly. When we listen to a classical work over and over again, we feel its new - new artistic facets.

Fourth: Music has an active emotional effect on children, delights and Awakens creative experiences. From good, meaningful, interesting music lessons, children get fun, get artistic feed, turn out cheerful, cheerful.

Fifth: the music lesson is closely related to other disciplines. Fine arts, literature, native language, mathematics, history, pedagogy, psychology, vocals, rhythmic, etc.

These will help you connect a music lesson with life, make it meaningful, interesting, and take the lesson. The music class also differs from other subjects in its mixed class type. In elementary grades, a music lesson is compiled from four types of activities:

1. *Music punctuation.*
2. *Sing as a team.*
3. *Music basket.*
4. *Music consists of creativity.*

When singing as a team, it is significant for the creative development of musical training of children. In this, being able to interest students in singing depends in many ways on each exercise or song that they learn to sing beautifully by the teacher. Because the vocal-choral work carried out with young children is often based on singing in imitation of the teacher's voice. Therefore, the teacher should regularly work on his pleasant voice. When performing vocal-choral work, the teacher: teaching the song in musical sentences (taking the right breath and saving the sentence to the end, working on the qualities of performance). Achieving the artistic performance of the song (conducting a short conversation on the impressions of children about the song i.e. generalization). Music basket. In the process of music culture classes, music savodi is used in the process of independent lesson activities to perform the work of artistic study and performance of a musical work on the basis of literacy. The content of the music basket increasingly shapes readers and deepens the scope of their work. Thus acts as an educational function of the lesson of the music savodi, the main basis and pedagogical purpose of the music savodi (activity) is carried out by literate analysis of works related to singing and listening to quarter topics given under the new program. They are taught based on the impressions and musical experiences that students receive from their daily lives. The music basket is taught in the following steps.

1. *Children's attention to train music expression tools melody, register, tempo, rhythm, dynamic characters.*
2. *Knowledge of the rules of sound tuning and singing, teaching to follow the rules of playing bats and instruments.*
3. *Music artists: "composer", "performer", "listener" information about the content of the topic and the authors of the work to be studied, is carried out through the music basket.*

Listening to music is the main factor in the lessons of listening to music, music culture, since the sound of music is consciously perceived and its character, content is consciously mastered. Based on the life experiences of the reader, the Zamiri of each musical work reflects a certain, feeling and thought. Each type of musical movement in which the course process is performed, musical plays, strengthen the memory of students, grow their speech, promote physical health and, by ruining them, increase their interest in the music lesson. Because, the attention of students of the beginner class is scattered, the sound apparatus is weak, the musical learning skills are not fully formed, they tend to be bright, playful. In this case, the structure of the lesson can be started from the activity of the lesson, which, depending on the pedagogical goals, is involved. The aim of this is to get students interested in music, to grow their musical abilities, to achieve a meaningfully logical whole by closely linking lesson activities with each other.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY.

Several musical literature was used on this article and I tried to state my views on the opinions and comments expressed in them. The music basket is very important as an activity that unites all activities. Because no matter what type of activity is used in the lesson, the work used in its practice is studied, and its distinctive features form new concepts that are about its genre, structure, content, musical signs, performers. Therefore, the music basket is not only made up of note basket styles, but is also a complex of knowledge concepts that make up the general musical knowledge of students. In my opinion, through the "music basket", it is advisable to instill knowledge about musical forms, genres, folk composition, composer's work, local styles of National Music, Classical Music in the reader's youth.

Results.

In this regard, every young specialist should know that the activity of the music basket is also important in the perception of music by students. Because it is in the process of mastering musical literacy that students realize that music differs

from other types of art in its means of expression, that is, "language" (melody, rhythm, dynamic signs, tempo, alternation signs, intervals), if fiction is expressed by word, visual art by color, dance art by movement, and music is expressed by the means of melody that

Discussion.

One of the main tasks of teachers of music culture of general secondary education schools is to bring students into the world of sophistication and provide spiritual education. In this, the teacher introduces children to a particular musical work, performing it in an expressive, lively way, attracting the attention of students to the work, influencing the growth of their speech, the expansion of thinking skills, worldview by teaching a good, meaningful piece of music. The content of music lessons involves not only mastering the topic, but also the development of the attitude of the consciousness of students to reality, the content and formation of their aesthetic culture. In this regard, the introduction of State Educational Standards in music education, among all academic disciplines, expands the possibilities of musical art. How much percentage does the quality efficiency of passing a music lesson show now? What is the level of interest of students in music? How are student appropriations assessed? In order to find answers to similar questions, it is advisable to analyze the topics of the primary school music basket in the program of music culture science of general secondary schools.

Conclusion.

In the processes of organizing the musical literacy of Primary School students in the science of "music culture", we noted that, while not every student is a musician, by understanding music science, he has the ability to see beauty in every seemingly simple thing. In this regard, we need to realize that working on oneself more than a teacher of music culture should be able to properly direct the child to acquire knowledge. V.A. Sukhomlinsky noted, "the lesson is a mirror of the general and pedagogical culture of the teacher, a measure of his intellectual wealth, an indicator of his worldview and erudition."

The musical culture of children of primary school age can be developed on the condition of targeted, systematic and planned Organization of educational work. The music teacher knows how important it is to have an interesting organization of musical-educational work during class time and after class. Then the teacher will be able to take advantage of the enormous possibilities of musical culture. We have witnessed that modern music pedagogy has a wide range of

opportunities for the development, education and education of knowledge and talent of schoolchildren.

We should also note that in the field of artistic and aesthetic education with the help of music, several directions are defined in modern pedagogy, and these directions are actively developing.

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